

First record of the crab spider *Diaea albicincta* Pavesi, 1883 from South Africa (Araneae: Thomisidae)

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Abstract: The African crab spider *Diaea albicincta* is known from Ethiopia and Tanzania. It is now for the first time recorded from South Africa. The general morphology is discussed with photographs of live specimens provided. Notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status are provided.

Key words: biodiversity, geographic distribution, South African National Survey of Arachnida

INTRODUCTION

The genus *Diaea* Thorell, 1869 is presently known from 46 species and three species are listed from South Africa (World Spider Catalogue, 2023). As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) large areas in South Africa was surveyed (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015) and several *Diaea* species have been collected. One of these species has been identified as *Diaea albicincta*, an African endemic described by Pavesi (1883) from Ethiopia from a male. Lessert (1919) described another male and the female from Mount Meru and Viboscho in Tanzania.

It is for the first time recorded from South Africa and the general morphology is discussed with photographs of live specimens provided as well as notes on their behaviour, distribution in South Africa and conservation status.

METHODS

Material was obtained from the SANSA surveys and voucher specimens are deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida at the Agricultural Research Council, Pretoria (NCA). Additional information was obtained from the SANSA Virtual Museum database (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2012).

TAXONOMY

Diaea albicincta Pavesi, 1883

Diaea albicincta Pavesi, 1883: 61 (m); Lessert, 1919: 141, f. 18–19, pl. 2, f. 31, 44 (m, f).

Diagnostic characters: Male (Figs 1 & 4) and female (Figs 2–3, 10 & 11). Body size: female 6–7 mm; male 5–6 mm. Male resemble the female but sometimes more brightly coloured. Carapace green with only the eye region covered by a brown patch; chelicerae green in female, in male with dark tint (Fig. 1). Abdomen oval, longer than wide; green with broad yellow-white area cover most of dorsal area; impose over the white area, abdomen decorated with a dark leaf like pattern that vary in shape between specimens, pattern usually edged with red brown. In a female collected at Wakefield farm, Kwa Zulu-Natal the specimen without distinct pattern on abdomen (Fig. 11). Legs green with a yellowish tint. In adults the legs I and II usually with distal end of leg segments with dark brown bands. In some males the femora ventrally with dark tint (Fig. 1). In immature specimens (Figs 11–12) the front legs without brown bands.

LIFE STYLE

Diaea albicincta is a free-living plant dweller that are active during the day. With their green colour they blend in with the vegetation.

Figures 1–3. *Diaea albicincta* 1 Male and 2. Female from Addo Elephant National Park. 3. Female from Karkloof. Photo credits: 1–2. Linda Wiese. 3. Rudi Steenkamp.

Figure 4–9. *Diaea albicincta* 4. Male habitus. 5–6. Male palp. 7. Female abdomen. 8. Epigyne. 9. Eye pattern.
Credits: 4–8 After Lessert (1919). 9. Peter Webb.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION

Ethiopia, Tanzania, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA

Eastern Cape: Addo Elephant National Park, Woody Cape (-33.88, 26.45) (Species was wrongly identified as *Diaea viridipes*); Gqeberha (Port Elizabeth) (-33.95, 25.61).

KwaZulu-Natal: Hillcrest, Farm Wakefield (-29.5, 29.90); Kloof (-29.78, 30.83); Karkloof (-29.30, 30.27). **Western Cape:** Gondwana Game Reserve, SE Herbertsdale (-34.07, 21.9); Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42).

CONSERVATION

An African endemic known from Ethiopia and Tanzania in the north and South Africa in the south. This species is under-collected and suspected to occur in more countries. Due to its wide range it is listed as Least Concern with no known threats.

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Figure 10–12. *Diaea albicincta*. 10. Female habitus from Kloof. 11. Immature female from Gondwana Game Reserve. 12. Immature female from Wakefield. Photo credits: 10. Bruce Blake. 11. 12. Peter Webb.